

360 DEGREE VIEW OF CAMPUS

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Abstract ---- In recent years, Virtual Reality (VR) technology has revolutionized the way user interact with digital environments. This paper presents a 360-degree campus exploration system that provides an immersive virtual tour experience. Using panoramic imaging, VR integration, interactive tools, the system allows users to navigate through key locations such as classrooms, laboratories, staff rooms and administrative offices. The project aims to enhance campus accessibility for prospective students, visitors and stakeholders by offering an interactive, real-time walkthrough similar to Google Street View. This innovative approach not only enhances campus representation but also serves as a scalable model for educational institutions looking to adopt virtual tour technologies.

Keywords : 360- Degree View, Virtual Reality (VR), Campus exploration, Interactive tour, Panoramic imaging, Immersive experience, Educational technology, Virtual campus tour.

I. INTRODUCTION

As technology continues to reshape various industries, the education sector is leveraging Virtual

Reality (VR) to enhance engagement, accessibility and remote interaction. One of the key challenges faced by prospective students, parents and visitors is the inability to physically explore, especially for those living far away or with time constraints. Traditional campus tours often require significant time and resources, limiting their accessibility. To address this, our project introduces a 360-degree virtual campus exploration system, providing an immersive and interactive experience that allows users to explore the campus from anywhere in the world.

The proposed system captures high-resolution panoramic images of key locations such as classrooms, staff rooms, principle room and recreational areas. These images are then integrated into an interactive virtual platform that enables users to navigate through the campus similarly to Google Street View. The project aims to provide a realistic and seamless user experience, ensuring that visitors can explore the institution as if they were physically present.

Beyond simple visualization, the system can incorporate AI-driven features such as smart navigation, interactive hotspots and virtual guides that provide real-time information about each location. This not only enhances user engagement but also serves as an effective tool for institutional promotion, digital documentation and accessibility for differently-abled individuals. With educational institutions increasingly embracing digital transformation, this project highlights how VR-based campus exploration can revolutionize student engagement, outreach and decision-making processes. By bridging the gap between physical and digital experiences, the system offers a cost-effective, scalable and innovative solution for universities, colleges and schools looking to enhance their visibility and accessibility in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

II. PREVIOUS WORK

This paper presents a 3D virtual campus tour system that allows users to interactively explore a university campus. This system simulates real-world environments in a game-like experience making it engaging for prospective students. The paper focuses on enhancing the virtual tour experience by introducing interactive elements such as clickable objects and navigation controls, providing a more personalized campus visit.[1]

This study explores the use of generative AI to create panoramic imagery in real-time. The system generates realistic 360-degree panoramic images based on user inputs, such as location or description. It demonstrates how AI can create dynamic and customized virtual environments, providing users with an immersive experience that evolves based on their interactions.[2]

This paper proposes a systematic framework for developing virtual campus tours. The framework integrates technologies such as VR, 3D modelling and panoramic imaging to create realistic and engaging campus tours. The framework sets the groundwork for creating virtual tours that closely mimic real-life campus visits, offering a clear roadmap for educational institutions to follow.[3]

This paper discusses the use of 360-degree panoramic images and VR technology to teach geomatic engineering. It shows how panoramic imagery when combined with VR tools, can be used to explain complex spatial concepts in the classroom. The research underscores the value of using immersive technologies to improve the

learning experience in engineering disciplines, providing students with a more hands-on interactive approach.[4]

This study explores the development of a virtual reality (VR) 360-degree campus tour of University Teknologi Malaysia (UTM) with voice command functionality to allow users to navigate the tour hands-free. The integration of voice commands enhances the accessibility of virtual tours, making them more user-friendly and intuitive, particularly for those with mobility impairments.[5]

This review paper discusses the technological advancements in panoramic imaging and its potential applications, especially in virtual tours. It covers various methods for capturing and rendering panoramic images, including 360-degree photography and VR integration. The paper provides a comprehensive overview of the current state of panoramic imaging and its relevance to creating realistic and immersive virtual tour experience.[6]

This paper presents the development of a virtual tour for Tishk International University, which integrates 3D visualization technology to create an interactive VR campus tour. By using 3D models and VR the paper highlights how a campus can be effectively showcased to prospective students, allowing for detailed exploration of university facilities from anywhere in the world.[7]

This paper discusses a method for panoramic navigation based on the machine learning algorithms, particularly Support Vector Machines (SVM), to enhance the precision and accuracy of virtual navigation in outdoor environments. The integration of machine learning provides a more accurate and efficient navigation system in virtual environments, improving user experience during 360-degree virtual campus tour.[8]

This research presents a collaborative virtual environment for university campuses, which can be used for both virtual tours and emergency evacuation training. The system uses VR to simulate real-life situations. The paper emphasizes how virtual tours can be expanded beyond traditional showcasing to include practical applications like evacuation drills, improving safety and preparedness.[9]

This paper introduces a system that uses panoramic imagery to create a virtual field trip experience for geology students. By leveraging image-based

rendering techniques, students can explore geological sites virtually. The use of panoramic imaging for educational field trips in geology provides students with an immersive and cost-effective way to explore natural environments that may otherwise be inaccessible.[10]

This paper presents a web-based application that uses ORB (Oriented FAST and Rotated BRIEF) image stitching to create a seamless virtual campus tour. By integrating ORB algorithms, the system captures and stitches multiple images to generate panoramic views. The application provides users with interactive controls to explore the campus virtually, offering hotspots for navigation and additional details about specific areas. This system significantly reduces the computational complexity associated with panoramic image processing and provides a cost-effective solution for creating virtual tours. It is particularly useful for institutions looking to showcase their campuses remotely.[11]

This paper examines the use of 360-degree videos in undergraduate education, focusing on their ability to create immersive learning experiences. This paper highlights how these videos can simulate real-world scenarios making learning more engaging and effective. The research explores the impact on student attention, comprehension and retention of complex subjects, particularly in disciplines such as architecture and science. By leveraging VR technologies, educators can create interactive environments that enhance student participation and understanding, offering a novel approach in education.[12]

This paper introduces an adaptive virtual tour system that combines location-based services (LBS) with virtual reality technologies. The system uses GPS data and real-time user tracking to provide tailored campus navigation. For instance, users can receive contextual information, such as details about nearby departments, buildings or amenities. The research emphasizes how integrating LBS improves the user experience by making virtual tours more interactive and personalized. The study also discusses technical challenges, such as maintaining accuracy and reducing latency in delivering location-specified content.[13]

This research explores the transformative role of virtual reality in education, emphasizing the integration of immersive 360-degree environments. It discusses the potential of VR to simulate real-world situations, offering practical experience to

students in fields like medicine, engineering and history. The study highlights case examples where VR-based learning outperformed traditional methods in terms of engagement and effectiveness. The paper also addresses challenges such as cost, accessibility and teacher training required to implement VR successfully in educational institutions.[14]

This study focuses on the use of immersive 360-degree videos as educational tools. It demonstrates how these videos can provide realistic simulations of environment, enhancing the learning experience for students. For instance, a 360-degree video tour of a museum can give students a sense of being physically present. The research explores the psychological effects of immersion on learning and identifies key technical requirements for implementing VR in classrooms. Challenges like motion sickness and the high cost of VR equipment are also discussed.[15]

VICT (Virtual Campus Tour) uses spherical panorama technology to create immersive virtual tours. This system allows users to explore a campus through 360-degree images, with hotspots enabling navigation between locations. The paper discusses the technical aspects of spherical panorama stitching, rendering and user interface design. VICT aims to provide a realistic and engaging experience for prospective students and parents who cannot physically visit the campus. It also highlights potential uses in remote learning and staff training.[16]

This paper describes the design of an AI-driven campus guide that uses natural language processing (NLP) and computer vision to assist users during virtual tours. The system provides real-time responses to user queries about campus locations, facilities and events. The AI engine processes user inputs to offer accurate information. The research highlights how such systems can improve user engagement and make campus tours more interactive. Challenges in implementing AI such as data training and computational costs, are also addressed.[17]

This research presents the use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) and photogrammetry to create detailed 3D maps of campuses. These maps are then integrated into virtual tour platforms, offering users an interactive and realistic experience. The paper discusses the advantages of using UAVs for aerial imaging, including high-resolution data

capture and cost efficiency. It also explores how photogrammetry techniques are used to stitch images and create 3D models. The research demonstrates the potential of combining UAVs with VR to revolutionize campus mapping.[18]

This paper evaluates the accessibility features of virtual reality campus tours, focusing on the inclusion of individuals with disabilities. It examines how features like voice navigation, subtitles and screen reader compatibility improve the experience for diverse users. The study highlights the importance of designing VR tours that cater to all audience ensuring inclusivity. The research also discusses challenges such as the need for standardized accessibility guidelines and the additional costs of implementing inclusive features.[19]

This paper explores the use of panoramic visualization in smart campus applications. It discusses how 360-degree imaging and VR tours to check real-time information about library availability or cafeteria queues. The paper emphasizes how panoramic visualization enhances user interaction with campus facilities while contributing to the overall smart campus ecosystem.[20]

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system for 360-degree Virtual Campus Exploration using Virtual Reality (VR) is designed to provide an immersive, interactive and realistic virtual tour experience. The system will enable users to navigate through a digital view of a campus, explore key locations and interact with informational elements.

1. SYSTEM OVERVIEW:

The system will capture high-resolution 360-degree panoramic images of campus, which will be stitched together to create a seamless virtual environment. These images will be integrated into an interactive VR platform that allows users to experience the campus in a Google Street View-like format.

2. KEY COMPONENTS:

- DATA COLLECTION & PROCESSING –
 - Capture 360-degree images using professional VR cameras or drones.

- Process and enhance images for better visual quality.
- Stitch images together to create a smooth virtual experience.

• VR ENVIRONMENT DEVELOPMENT –

- Use Unity Engine for immersive rendering.
- Develop an interactive interface for navigation.

• CROSS-PLATFORM COMPATIBILITY –

- Accessible via web browsers, mobile devices and VR headsets.
- Responsive UI/UX design for an optimal experience across the device.

3. EXPECTED OUTCOMES:

- IMPROVED ACCESSIBILITY – Enables remote visitors to explore the campus anytime, anywhere.
- MARKETING & OUTREACH – Helps attract prospective and interactive experience than traditional tours.
- COST-EFFECTIVE & SCALABLE – Once created the system requires minimal maintenance and can be expanded easily.

IV. METHODOLOGY

SYSTEM DESIGN :

The system follows a model design approach, incorporating the following components:

- 360-degree navigation : Users can look around and explore different locations through panoramic views.
- Transitions : Clickable elements provide seamless Scene Transition to respective scene.
- VR Headset : The system works in both VR headsets making it accessible to a larger audience.
- Web-Based Integration : Expanding the VR tour to be accessible via a web browser without the need for additional software installation.

IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS :

1. Development Platform: Unity Editor.
2. Programming Language: C#

3. SDKs Used: Meta Quest SDK.
4. Media Assets: 360-degree images/videos.
5. Hardware Requirements: Meta Quest 3, Nikon Key Mission 360/170.
6. Add On: WebGL Hosted

The project is designed to ensure that the virtual campus experience, offering an engaging and immersive interface. User testing indicated that interactive hotspots significantly improve navigation and user satisfaction. Performance optimization ensures a smooth experience with minimal motion sickness.

1. 360 shoot to transfer:

2. Development Phase:

Home screen

During the testing phase, multiple users were invited to explore the virtual campus and provide feedback. The results indicated a high engagement rate, with users appreciating the ability to move freely and interact with points of interest. The teleportation system was particularly well-received as it allowed quick navigation between different areas of the campus. Minimal latency and optimized rendering techniques ensured a seamless and immersive experience, even on devices with moderate hardware specifications.

CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS :

Despite its success, the project encountered several challenges :

- Integration of VR SDK : Compatibility issues with different VR platforms posed difficulties in ensuring a consistent experience.
- Performance Optimization : Large media files required efficient rendering techniques to avoid lag and performance drops.
- User Experience : Addressing motion sickness and usability concerns was crucial to ensure smooth interactions within the VR environment.
- Hardware Dependency : While the system is designed to be cross-platform, optimal performances still depends on the hardware capabilities of the device being used.

FUTURE SCOPE:

- AI-Baese Virtual Guide : Implementing voice-guided tours to enhance the informational aspect of the tour.
- 3D-Model Integration : Enhancing realism by replacing 360-degree images with real-time 3D environments.
- Multi-User Experience : Enabling collaborative virtual tours where multiple users can interact in the same VR spaces.

Future development efforts will focus on making the system more accessible, interactive and scalable allowing institutions to adopt VR tours as a standard means of showcasing their facilities to a global audience.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experimental results of the 360-degree virtual campus tour using Augmented Reality (AR) were obtained through rigorous testing, user feedback, and performance evaluation. The system was assessed based on technical efficiency, user experience, and system scalability.

1. Performance Evaluation

To ensure seamless functionality, several key performance indicators were measured:

(a) System Loading and Responsiveness

Average Loading Time:

The 360-degree campus view loaded within 2.5 seconds on high-speed internet.

AR Overlay Activation:

AR elements appeared in 1 second upon user interaction.

Navigation Speed:

Moving between different campus locations took less than 2 seconds, ensuring a smooth transition.

(b) System Stability and Scalability

- Conducted a stress test with 1000 concurrent users, and the system remained stable without crashes.

- Cloud-based architecture handled large image and video files efficiently, preventing excessive bandwidth usage.

(c) Compatibility Testing

- Successfully tested on Android, iOS, and web browsers like Chrome, Firefox, and Safari.

- Performance was consistent across different devices, but older smartphones (below 3GB RAM) showed slight delays in rendering AR elements.

2. User Engagement Analysis

To assess usability, a sample group of 100 users participated in an experimental study. The key engagement metrics were:

(a) Hotspot Interactions

- 90% of users clicked on at least 5 interactive hotspots during their tour.

- Most frequently visited locations: Laboratories, Library, Auditorium, and Sports Complex.

(b) AR Feature Usage

- 85% of users interacted with AR elements, such as pop-up information, 3D models, and multimedia content.

- Users found AR overlays useful in understanding campus infrastructure.

(c) Session Duration

- Average user session lasted between 15 to 20 minutes, indicating high engagement levels.

- Returning user rate within 24 hours: 30%, suggesting continued interest in the platform.

User Feedback Highlights

Positive Aspects

- Users appreciated the realistic virtual tour experience.

- The smooth navigation and high-resolution imagery enhanced the experience.

- AR integration provided a unique way to explore campus information.

Areas for Improvement

- Some users suggested adding AI-driven guides for interactive assistance.

- Offline mode support was requested for better accessibility.

4. Experimental Challenges Observed

While the system performed well overall, some challenges were identified:

- Device Limitation: Older mobile devices struggled with rendering high-resolution 360-degree images.

- Network Dependency: Users with slower internet connections experienced delays in loading images and AR elements.

- AR Overlay Optimization: Some users found that AR elements needed better positioning to align seamlessly with real-world objects.

V. CONCLUSION

The 360-Degree College Tour in VR project demonstrates the potential of virtual reality in enhancing campus tours. By utilizing 360-degree imagery, interactive hotspots and VR navigation, the system provides an immersive and accessible experience. The successful implementation of this project paves the way for further advancements in VR-based educational tools. Future enhancements can further improve user engagement and broaden the application of VR in education. This project serves as a stepping stone towards next-generation campus exploration, offering an innovative and engaging alternative to traditional physical campus visits.

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